

HISTORY AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE ART OF BAKSHI

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ABSTRACT

This article is about the great examples of folklore, epic poetry and their schools, the history of the origins of the art of bakhshi, the stages of development and its significance today.

Bakhshi, which is a highly professional art of folklore, is associated with the development of epics and the names of bakhshis. Bakhshi, who played an important role in the cultural and political life of the people, were highly respected and respected among the working people. Epics created from the lamentations of the people's hearts have been passed down from generation to generation and have served for the spiritual upliftment of mankind. Because our epics contain very rich and ancient traditions of artistic thinking of our people. The artistic traditions of the art of epic poetry have survived for centuries with the unique practice and tireless work of folk singers. In this way, the most beautiful, the best national songs and epics delight the audience with their power and charm. From time immemorial, they have touched the most delicate bonds of the human soul, sharing aesthetic and spiritual

nourishment. In the Uzbek language, he is considered to be an artist who sings, memorizes and transmits folk epics in a broad sense. According to H.T. Zarifov, bakhshi is derived from the words "mogulcha" and "buryatcha" bakhsha, bagsha, meaning master, enlightener. In some sources, the word bakhshi comes from the Chinese word pak-si and means teacher, writer, secretary. Among the people, the word bakhshi is used to refer to a person who performs two different functions. In many places it is used to refer to a professional narrator, and in some places to a shaman.

Later, there was a certain separation in the profession. The bakhshis are divided into performer and creative bakhshis, and the bakhshis sing mainly the epics they have learned from their masters, with minor variations. Creative poets, on the other hand, create their own versions of the epic based on the oral epic tradition, and even

create new epics based on them. When we say Bakhshi, we involuntarily see the image of a wise man with a white beard, a talker, and a drummer who plays the drums with pleasure. However, not only drums but also other musical instruments are used to perform bakhshis. Bakhshis laugh at epics and songs not only with drums, but also with words such as kobiz and dutar. In some places, bakhshis are called by various words such as kushnoch, duoxon, kinnachi. This difference is evident in some Turkic peoples. In Turkmen, for example, a professional poet is called "afsungar", "duoxon", "fortune teller" in Kazakh and Kyrgyz. But the well-known Uzbek bakhshis and their teachers did not combine the art of bakhshis with the task of caring for the sick with the help of various spells. However, there is some information about the poets who combined the art of epic poetry with the practice of prayer, and in the distant past, Uzbek poets, like many other peoples, must have performed both functions equally. For this reason, Professor ERTenishev said that the word "baxshi" in the Eastern dialect of the Uyghur language means "doctor", shaman in the Dolan dialect "magician", "fortune teller" in the Uyghur memoirs "teacher", "student". he stressed. The fact that a number of bakhshis still keep their art a secret and "deify" it is evidenced by various popular myths about the art of bakhshis.

Bakhshis are called by different names not only by the Turkic peoples, but also in some parts of Uzbekistan. For example, in some parts of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya they are called "centurion", among the Uzbeks of southern Tajikistan - "soqi", in the Fergana valley - "enumerator", in some districts - "jirov",

"jirovchi", "aqin". In folk art, poets who are able to create their own new versions and even new epics within the epic tradition are called poets, and the above-mentioned creative poets are poets. They took the lead in singing epic works among a wide range of workers. Research by scholars such as Khodi Zarif, B. Karimov, and M. Saidov shows that in the 19th and early 20th centuries, the repertoire of Uzbek bakhshis included about one hundred and fifty epics. Our folklorists have recorded about a hundred of them. To date, these figures acknowledge that about three hundred epic names have been identified. Bakhshi's repertoire includes all the works that he has mastered and sung creatively. The repertoire of Uzbek folk singers is extremely limited by genre. They sang works of folklore in two genres, namely, epics and epics. The Bakhshi did not recite "tales", "songs", "anecdotes", etc., except for the national anthem and the epic. But such a statement was not appropriate for a professional narrator. It should be noted that some epics have come down to us only in content. The epic "Oysuluv" is one of such works. The size of the Bakhshi repertoire is not the same either. Ordinary bakhshis usually knew five or ten epics. Even then, they sang a couple of epics well. The repertoire of the most talented and gifted artists included thirty, forty and more epics. According to sources, the poet Polkan, who has an extraordinary memory, memorized more than seventy epics. Considering that each epic contains from two to three thousand lines, from ten to fifteen or even twenty thousand lines, the lion has almost as many prose parts. It will be obvious. Polkan poet, who created in the middle of the XX century, 76, Fozil Yuldosh oglu 60, Ergash Jumanbulbul oglu 50,

Mardonaqul Avliyokul oglu 43, Bola bakhshi 20, epic, Kadyr Bakhshi, who wrote in the second half of the 20th century in the 60s and 70s, memorized 62 epics, the Stone Poet 20, and Saidmurad Panoh oglu 12 12 epics. Uzbek epics have a traditional singing style. All the listeners were sitting in a row in the hotel offered by Bakhshi. Bakhshi was put in the net. During the performance, the narrator finds the right words and melodies for each picture. In their own words, it "boils". At such times, no one notices that the spectator is out of the net. Epic nights in a well-invited village or house sometimes last several days. Such nights are held in the late fall and early spring evenings. Bakhshis love to sing epics that reflect devotion to the country, courage, bravery, kindness, humanity and generosity, friendship and brotherhood. Specific schools of baxshi art have been formed in Karakalpakstan, Khorezm, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya and Samarkand regions of the country. They differ from each other in their uniqueness. At present, there are baxshich schools in Bulungur, Qurghon, Shakhrisabz, Kamay, Sherabad, South Tajikistan, and Khorzam. Representatives of the Bulungur School of Poetry, for example, became famous for their heroic epics. The professional creator of this school is the son of the talented donor Fozil Yuldash. Representatives of the Khorzam School of Poetry perform mainly music, memorizing texts. When the dutar is used by a soloist on a musical instrument, it acts as a snare drum and a child snare drum. Another distinctive feature of the Khorezm school is that it sings as a group. This school repertoire is also different from other schools. For example, the heroic epic "Alpomish" is not found here, on the contrary, most of the romantic novels do

not exist in other parts of the country. The performances of the oasis baxshi schools are accompanied by drums, a song in a muffled voice, and a poem in an open voice. One of the unique schools of the oasis is Sherabad School of Poetry. The history, evolution, influence and scope of the Sherabad school of epic poetry play an important role in Uzbek folklore. The founder of the Sherabad School of Poetry is Sherna Bakhshi (son of Shernazar Beknazar). In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Sherna Bakhshi Umir Bakhshi, Kholiyor Bakhshi, Mardonakul Avliyokul oglu, Kara Bakhshi, Mamarayim Bakhshi, and Boymurod Bakhshi worked together around this school. The Sherabad School of Poetry covers the Surkhandarya oasis, southern Tajikistan, southeastern Turkmenistan, and northern Afghanistan.

Bakhshi poets united in Sherabad school of epic poetry: "Alpomish", "Hasankhan", "Nurali", "Yunus pari", "Misqol pari". The epics "Golden Pumpkin", "Malla Sabdogar", "Ollanazar Olchinbek", "Toshbosar", and "Khursona" from the repertoire of the Sherabad School of Poetry are not found in the repertoire of other bakhshis. One of the largest representatives of this school today is the People's Bakhshi of Uzbekistan Shoberdi Bakhshi Boltaboyev. The epics he sang are distinguished by their artistic perfection and charm. In his works, he sang the epics "Alpomish", "Avazkhan", "Kuntugmush", "Oyparcha" with great pleasure. Bakhshu must have mastered the art of memorization, knowing the life and culture of the people, the history, customs, traditions and rhetoric of the country where the blood was shed. He must be able to use proverbs, sayings, puns and allusions of various forms of the

vernacular. One of the main requirements of telling a story is to make it attractive and interesting, to be able to capture the heart of the listener, to captivate him, to find the melody. During the years of independence, a lot of work has been done to revive and develop the folklore. In particular, on November 6, 1999, in collaboration with UNESCO, the 1000th anniversary of the epic "Alpomish" was celebrated. The epic was published in different languages, and statues were erected on it. However, Alpomish has survived to the present day thanks to the oral art of the Bakhshi and has become a universal cultural heritage and spiritual property. In the history of culture of Uzbekistan in the XIX-XX centuries, as mentioned above, the names of many great poets have been mentioned, and their epics, poems, epics have been published in tapes, records and collections. In 2000, the title of "People's Bakhshi" was established in our republic, the only one established in any country for our bakhshis, who have such tariffs as the speaker, the answer, the wise man. In 2001, Boysun was recognized by UNESCO as a "Pearl of the Oral and Spiritual Heritage of Humanity", and in 2002, the Boysun Spring Folklore Festival was held in Boysun. Attention to art and culture plays an important role in the reforms being carried out in our country today. The role of our poets in promoting the masterpieces of folklore in the oasis to the general public is commendable. Holding the International Festival of Bakhshi Art, preservation and development of unique examples of Uzbek national art of Bakhshi and epic, its widespread promotion, strengthening the sense of respect and attention to this art in the hearts of the younger generation, strengthening the ties of friendship and

brotherhood between different peoples has become an important factor in further expanding internationally in the framework of cultural enlightenment relations. It is the duty of each of us to inherit from our great ancestors the power to create civilizations between great rivers, such as the Jaihun and the Sayhun, and to pass it on to the next generation. A lot of work has been done in this direction in our country. The 16th session of the Intergovernmental Committee for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of UNESCO, held in Paris in December 2021, unanimously approved the proposal of UNESCO to include the art of Bakhchisarai in the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. The ancient history and culture of each nation and, first of all, its oral creativity are embodied in folk tales and epics, which are invaluable in understanding the identity of the nation, preserving and developing its unique national values and traditions. is the source.

This unique heritage, which meets all the criteria for inclusion in the UNESCO World Heritage List, is rare in the world and has been preserved for thousands of years. This decision of UNESCO was a recognition of the art of baxshi in the world. This age-old value is now evolving in the eyes of the international community. It is especially gratifying that in recent years, the idea of strengthening the deep understanding of nationalism and pride in national values among young people, conveying to the world community the evidence that our country is one of the first cradles of human culture is being put forward directly by our President. The concept of the "art of giving"

is now widely promoted through UNESCO, and most importantly, the culture does not disappear, but develops. . In particular, the "School of Arts Specializing in Bakhshi" in the oasis plays an important role in educating talented bakhshis who skillfully sing epics and folk songs, which have become masterpieces based on centuries-old traditions. In this regard, I talked to Zulhumor Bakhshi (Zulhumor Shernazarova), a senior specialist teacher at the school, about the secrets of baxshi and their dreams. They were honored to say that Bakhshi was an ancestral profession passed down from generation to generation. He has been practicing witchcraft for 41 years and has memorized more than 10 epics and about 100 poems. It is said that when I was in the 4th and 5th grades, I learned many terms and epics from Almighty God, and he was recognized as my teacher. Bakhshi's secret is well-known, so it's difficult for anyone to master

the field. They fill the hearts with the magic melody and unique melodies of the dombra. Proud of the attention paid to this area, the head of our state has created such opportunities for us. In our country, baxshi has become an art with its own traditions, schools and prospects. To further develop this field, in order to teach students to love this art, it is necessary to organize master classes on witchcraft in art schools, secondary schools and preschools. I would like to suggest the organization of Bakhshi Day to further illuminate the prospects of this art.

Bakhshi events, creative evenings, and a competition of essays on the theme of our millennial epics and national teams will be an important foundation for the development of the industry. Epics and epics that have lived for centuries serve as an important tool for understanding the national identity and promoting Uzbek traditions.

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